

IQLIM OMILLARINING YOG‘OCH SIFATIGA TA’SIRI: TAHLIL VA ISTIQBOLLAR.

Jo‘rayev Ulug‘bek Inomiddin o‘g‘li

jorayevulugbek525@gmail.com

Namangan muhandislik-qurilish instituti o‘qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada iqlim omillarining yog‘och sifatiga ta’siri tahlil qilinadi, shuningdek, ushbu sohadagi istiqbollari ko‘rib chiqiladi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *Yog‘och, sifat, iqlim omillari, tahlil, mustahkamlik.*

Yog‘och turli xil sanoat va qurilishlarda keng qo‘llaniladigan asosiy tabiiy resurslardan biridir. Yog‘ochning sifati uning mustahkamligi, chidamliligi va estetik xususiyatlarini muhim ahamiyatga ega. Biroq, yog‘ochning sifati daraxtlar o‘sadigan iqlim sharoitiga qarab juda farq qilishi mumkin.

Yog‘ochning tuzilishi va xususiyatlarini shakllantirishda harorat, yog‘ingarchilik, namlik va quyosh nurlari kabi iqlim omillari muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Masalan, yuqori harorat va namlik yetishmasligi yog‘och diametrining pasayishiga va yog‘och zichligining oshishiga olib kelishi mumkin. Yog‘ingarchilik va namlikdagi og‘ishlar, yog‘och tuzilishida yoriqlar paydo bo‘lishiga olib kelishi mumkin. Quyosh nurlanishi yog‘ochning mustahkamligi va barqarorligiga ta’sir qiluvchi kechikishning shakllanishiga ta’sir qiladi. [1,2,3]

Tashqi sharoitlar daraxtlarning o‘shishiga turli xil ta’sir ko‘rsatadi. Havoning harorati va yog‘ingarchilik kabi meteorologik sharoitlar bilvosita daraxt tanasi massasining o‘shishiga ta’sir qiladi. Hozirgi radial o‘shish va meteorologik omillar o‘rtasidagi kuzatilgan munosabatlar statistikdir [4,5,6]

O‘z tadqiqotlarida Sennikova A. A. (2023) va Aleksandrov R. A. (2023) yog‘ochning makrostrukturaviy elementlarining o‘rtacha harorati bilan kuchli to‘g‘ridan-to‘g‘ri bog‘liqlikni kuzatdilar. O‘shish davrida qoraqarag‘ayning yillik o‘shishi harorat o‘zgarishiga yuqori javob beradi [7,8]

O‘z tadqiqotlari natijalariga ko‘ra, Yanush S. Y. (2023) qoraqarag‘ay va qarag‘ay yog‘ochining zichligiga daraxtning ekishdagi kattaligi, ya’ni ma’lum bir magistralning diametri eng katta ta’sir ko‘rsatishini ta’kidlaydi. Bu shuni anglatadiki, magistral diametri qanchalik katta bo‘lsa, yog‘och zichligi shunchalik yuqori bo‘ladi. Ushbu omil yog‘ochning sifatini va uning turli maqsadlarda ishlatilishini baholashda muhim rol o‘ynaydi [9,10]

Iqlim omillarining yog‘och sifatiga ta’sirini tahlil qilish uchun turli usul va yondashuvlar qo‘llaniladi. Eng keng tarqalgan usullardan biri bu daraxt halqalarini o‘rganishga asoslangan dendroxronologiyadir. Daraxt halqalarining kengligi va tuzilishini tahlil qilish orqali iqlim sharoitining daraxt o‘shishi va yog‘och sifatiga ta’sirini aniqlash mumkin. Yana bir usul-bu yog‘ochning kimyoviy tarkibini tahlil qilish, bu iqlim omillari va zichlik, tsellyuloza tarkibi va o‘shish chiziqlari kabi yog‘och xususiyatlari o‘rtasidagi bog‘liqlikni aniqlashga imkon beradi.[11,12,13]

Iqlim omillarining yog‘och sifatiga ta’siri bo‘yicha tadqiqotlar o‘rmon resurslarini boshqarish strategiyasini ishlab chiqishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ushbu munosabatlarni tushunish o‘zgaruvchan iqlim sharoitida yog‘och sifatidagi o‘zgarishlarni bashorat qilish imkonini beradi. Bu o‘rmon xo‘jaligini rejalashtirishda, optimal daraxt turlarini tanlashda va yog‘ochni qayta ishlash va saqlash usullarini ishlab chiqishda foydali bo‘lishi mumkin. Bundan tashqari, yog‘och sifatini yaxshilash qurilish va ishlab chiqarishda innovatsion materiallar va texnologiyalarni rivojlantirishga yordam beradi. [14,15]

Shunday qilib, iqlim omillari yog‘och sifatiga sezilarli ta’sir ko‘rsatadi degan xulosaga kelish mumkin. Iqlim sharoiti va yog‘ochning xususiyatlari o‘rtasidagi bog‘liqlikni tahlil qilish yog‘ochni shakllantirish jarayonlarini chuqurroq tushunishga va uning sifatini yaxshilash choralarini ko‘rishga imkon beradi. [16,17]

Ushbu sohadagi tadqiqotlar barqaror o‘rmon xo‘jaligini rivojlantirish uchun juda muhimdir. Iqlim

omillaring yog'och sifatiga ta'sirini tushunish o'zgaruvchan iqlim sharoitlarini hisobga oladigan o'rmon resurslarini boshqarish strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishga imkon beradi. Bunga ko'proq moslashuvchan daraxt turlarini tanlash, o'rmonlarni yetishtirish va parvarish qilish usullarini optimallashtirish va iqlim omillaring yog'och sifatiga salbiy ta'sirini kamaytirish choralarini ishlab chiqish kiradi. [18,19]

Bundan tashqari, iqlimning yog'ochga ta'siri bo'yicha tadqiqotlar sanoat va qurilishda innovatsion yechimlarda qo'llaniladi. Iqlim omillari yog'ochning xususiyatlariga qanday ta'sir qilishini tushunish ushbu ta'sirlarni hisobga oladigan yangi materiallar va texnologiyalarni ishlab chiqishga imkon beradi. Bu yanada mustahkam, barqaror va bardoshli materiallarga, shuningdek, energiya tejaydigan va ekologik jihatdan barqaror qurilish yechimlarini ishlab chiqishga olib kelishi mumkin. [20]

Umuman olganda, iqlim omillaring yog'och sifatiga ta'sirini o'rganish barqaror o'rmon xo'jaligi va sanoat va qurilishda innovatsion yechimlarni rivojlantirishga yordam beradigan muhim yo'nalishdir. Bu o'rmon resurslaridan yanada samarali foydalanish, mahsulot sifatini yaxshilash va atrof-muhitga salbiy ta'sirini kamaytirish imkonini beradi. Ushbu sohadagi keyingi tadqiqotlar va ishlanmalar barqaror va ekologik mas'uliyatli kelajakni yaratish istiqbollari ochib beradi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR:

1. Ловелиус Н. В. Изменения прироста годичных колец сосны и ели в восточноевропейской тайге в связи с географическими факторами среды / Н. В. Ловелиус, С. И. Лежнева; Российский государственный педагогический университет им. А. И. Герцена Вологодский государственный университет Петровская академия наук и искусств. — Санкт-Петербург, Вологда: Вологодская областная научная библиотека, 2015.
2. Юлдашев, Ж., Каюмов, Д., & Жураев, У. (2021). Олий таълим муассасаси профессор ўқитувчисининг маъруза ўтиш услуги ва ўзини тутиши. *Экономика и социум*, (1-2 (80)), 813-817.
3. Юлдашев, Ж., Каюмов, Д., & Жураев, У. (2021). Ўқув жараёнини илмий асосда ташкил этишда талабаларнинг мустақил таълимини ривожлантиришнинг услубий асослари. *Экономика и социум*, (1-2 (80)), 802-806.
4. Anvarzhon, D., & Abdukhalikovich, X. M. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF RAVAGED LAND PLOTS, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT SOIL AND WATER CONSERVATION AGRICULTURE (NAMANGAN ADYRS). *Journal of new century innovations*, 38(2), 109-112.
5. Дадаходжаев, А., Хамракулов, М., & Жўраев, У. (2022, September). ЭКОЛОГИК ТОЗА МАҲСУЛОТ ЕТИШТИРИШДА ЎСИМЛИКЛАРНИ ТУПРОҚ ВА ОЗУҚА ТАЛАБЛАРИНИ БОШҚАРИШ. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE DEDICATED TO THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATION IN THE 21ST CENTURY* (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 80-83).
6. Дадахўжаев, А., & Жўраев, У. И. Ў. (2022). Повышение плодородия засоленных почв в сельском хозяйстве наманганских адыров, размещением на основе севооборотов. *Механика и технология*, (Спецвыпуск 1), 118-122.
7. Muhammadali, R. A., Juraev, U. I. U., & Nurekeshev, S. S. O. (2021). Influence of seasonal mud of the Narin river for the coagulation process. *ASIAN JOURNAL OF MULTIDIMENSIONAL RESEARCH*, 10(5), 69-72.
8. U.I.Jo'rayev, A.A.Abdulakimov, & N.F.Allamurodov. (2023). EKOLOGIK MUAMMOLARNI BARTARAF ETISHDA MUQOBIL ENERGIYA . *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 2(16), 262–265.
9. Nurmuxamad Najmitdinovich Majidov, Dilshod Abdug'Ofur O'G'Li Qayumov, & Ulug'Bek Inomiddin O'G'Li Jo'Rayev (2023). TA'LIM SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA ZAMONAVIY PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALARNING AHAMIYATI. *Oriental Art and Culture*, 4 (2), 441-446.

10. Alisher Xaydaraliyevich Alinazarov, Dilshod Abdug'Ofur O'G'Li Qayumov, & Ulug'Bek Inomiddin O'G'Li Jo'Rayev (2023). O'ZBEKISTON OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMIDA FAN, TA'LIM VA ISHLAB CHIQRISH INTEGRATSIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI. *Oriental Art and Culture*, 4 (2), 234-240.

11. Dadakhodzhaev Anvarzhon, & Juraev Ulugbek. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF RAVINE LANDS TAKING INTO ACCOUNT SOIL PROTECTION AGRICULTURE OF THE CHARTAK ADYRS. *Proceedings of International Conference on Scientific Research in Natural and Social Sciences*, 2(12), 193–197.

12. Dadakhodzhaev Anvarzhon, Xamrakulov Mansurjon Abdukhalikovich, Juraev Ulugbek Inomiddin ugli, & Abdulakimov Abdulaziz Abdumutal ugli. (2023). PRINCIPLES OF IMAGE EROSION MANAGEMENT OF NAMANGAN ADYRS OF UZBEKISTAN. *Proceedings of Scientific Conference on Multidisciplinary Studies*, 2(12), 121–125.

13. У.И.Жураев, А.А.Абдулакимов, & М.Р.Тўхтабоев. (2023). ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ВЫСОКОПОТЕНЦИАЛЬНЫХ ВТОРИЧНЫХ. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 2(16), 257–261.

14. Melibaev Makhmudzhon, Dadahodjaev Anvar, & Jorayev Ulugbek Inomiddin ugli. (2023). Indicators Of Average Life Of Tractor Pneumatic Tires Under Cotton Processing Conditions. *Journal of Advanced Zoology*, 44(S7), 1027–1032.

15. Abdullayev Muhammadali Rustamjonovich, Jorayev Ulugbek Inomiddin Ogli. (2022). [AHOLINI TOZA ICHIMLIK SUVI BILAN TAMINLASHDA SUV OLIISH MANBAALARINING ORNI](#). *Ta'lim fidoyilari*, 6(7)107-110.

16. Dadakhodzhaev Anvarzhon., Hamrakulov Mansurjon Abdukhalikovich., Juraev Ulugbek Inomiddin ugli. (2023). GULLY EROSION AND THEIR DENSITY MAPPING. *International scientific-online conference: INTELLECTUAL EDUCATION TECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS AND INNOVATIVE DIGITAL TOOLS*. 103-109

17. Xabibullayevich, M. M. (2023). SANOAT CHIQINDI SUVLARNI QAYTA ISHLASH SISTEMASI. *Journal of new century innovations*, 38(2), 101-108.

18. Dadakhodzhaev, A., Xamrakulov, M. A., Mirsaidov, M., & Abdulakimov, A. (2023). INCREASING IN FERTILITY, MELIORATIVE STATE OF SALINE SOILS DUE TO THE ORDER OF PRIORITY. SEEDING OF AGRICULTURAL CROPS. *Journal of new century innovations*, 38(2), 96-100.

19. Maxmudjon, M., Numonjonovna, D. M., & Abdumutal o'g'li, A. A. (2023). KALSIY VA AMMONIY NITRATLARNI ETANOL ISHTIROKIDA EKSTRAKTSIYALASHNI TADQIQ QILISH. *PEDAGOG*, 6(11), 230-236.

20. Xabibullayevich, M. M., Numonjonovna, D. M., & Abdumutal o'g'li, A. A. (2023). OHAKTOSH ASOSIDA KALSIY NITRAT ISHLAB CHIQRISH XOSSALARI VA TEXNOLOGIYASI. *PEDAGOG*, 6(11), 225-229.

21. Dilobar S. TALABA QIZLARDAN AN' ANAVIY BO' LMAGAN SPORT TURLARI BILAN SHUG' ULLANISHNING BUGUNGI KUNDAGI AHAMIYATI //Uz-Conferences. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 783-786.

22. Dilobar S. The Importance of Physical Activity in Improving Public Health //Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 16-18.

23. Dilobar S. The Importance of Physical Activity in Improving Population Health //JOURNAL OF SCIENCE, RESEARCH AND TEACHING. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 19-21.

24. ТОМЧИЛАТИБ СУҒОРИШ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИ ОРҚАЛИ СУҒОРИЛГАН ОЛМА БОҒЛАРИНИНГ ТУПРОҚ АГРОКИМЁВИЙ КЎРСАТГИЧЛАРИ. In Proceedings of International Conference on Educational Discoveries and Humanities (Vol. 2, No. 11, pp. 19-23).

25. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш. (2019). EFFICIENCY OF USE OF CLAY WATER WITH DROP IRRIGATION. ЖУРНАЛ АГРО ПРОЦЕССИНГ, (4).

26. Xudayev, I. J., & Tojiyev, S. M. (2023). NAMLATGICH-BLOKLARDAN HOSIL QILINGAN EKTRANLI EGATLARDAN G‘O‘ZANI SUG‘ORISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. In Uz-Conferences (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 514-519).

27. Худайев, И., & Фазлиев, Ж. ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ КАПЕЛЬНОГО ОРОШЕНИЯ САДОВ И ВИНОГРАДНИКОВ. JURNALI, 176

28. Fazliyev, J. (2017). Drip irrigation technology in gardens. Интернаука. Science Journal, 7(11).

29. Fazliyev, J. (2018). Modern irrigation methods for gardens. Science, 22, 24-26.

30. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш., & Баратов, С. С. (2014). ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ГЛИНИСТОЙ ВОДЫ ПРИ КАПЕЛЬНОМ ОРОШЕНИИ. The Way of Science, (4), 77.

31. Fazliyev, J. EFFICIENCY OF APPLYING THE WATER-SAVING IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGIES IN IRRIGATED FARMING «ИНТЕРНАУКА» Science Journal № 21 (103) June 2019 г.

32. Khudaev, I., & Fazliev, J. (2022). Water-saving irrigation technology in the foothill areas in the south of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Современные инновации, системы и технологии, 2(2), 0301-0309

33. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш. (2017). Боғларда томчилатиб суғориш технологияси. Интернаука, (7-3), 71-73.

34. Худайев, И., & Тожиев, Ш. (2023). БОҒ ВА УЗУМЗОРЛАРДА ТОМЧИЛАТИБ СУҒОРИШ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИНИ ЖОРИЙ ҚИЛИШНИНГ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ. Talqin Va Tadqiqotlar, 1(1). извлечено от <https://talqinvatadqiqotlar.uz/index.php/tvt/article/view/220>

35. Фазлиев Жамолиддин, Тожиев Шерзод, & Холиқов Шарифбек. (2024). СПОСОБЫ ЭКОНОМИИ ВОДНЫХ РЕСУРСОВ В САДАХ. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 520–525. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/110>

36. J.Sh.Fazliyev., Sh.M.Tojiev., Sh.D.Khalikov. (2024). EFFICIENCY OF USE OF CLAY WATER WITH DROP IRRIGATION. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 504–509. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/107>

37. I.J.Xudayev, I.J.Xudayev, & Sh.M.Tojiyev. (2024). NAMLATGICH-BLOKLARDAN HOSIL QILINGAN EKTRANLI EGATLARDAN G‘O‘ZANI SUG‘ORISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 514–519. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/109>

38. Khamidov, M. K., Juraev, U. A., Buriev, X. B., Juraev, A. K., Saksonov, U. S., Sharifov, F. K., & Isabaev, K. T. (2023, February). Efficiency of drip irrigation technology of cotton in saline soils of Bukhara oasis. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1138, No. 1, p. 012007). IOP Publishing.

39. Sharifov Firdavs, & Mirzamurotov Mirshod. (2024). G‘O‘ZA O‘SIMLIGINI YETISHTIRISHDA SUV TEJAMKOR SUG‘ORISH TEXNOLOGIYALARINI QO‘LLASH. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 461–464. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/98>

40. Sattorovich, S. U., & Qobil o‘g‘li, S. F. (2022). BUG‘DOY O‘SIMLIGI VA DONINING XALQ XO‘JALIGIDA BUGUNGI KUNDAGI AHAMIYATI.

41. Xamrayev Kamol, Sharifov Firdavs, & Yusupova Oynura. (2024). TUPROQ SHO‘RINI YUVISHDA BIOSOLVENT BIRIKMASINI TUPROQ SUV-TUZ MUVOZANATIGA TA‘SIRI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 458–460. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/97>

42. Shodiev, Z. O., Inoyatov, I. S., & Shodiev, N. S. (2020). NATURAL PASTE AND ITS VALUE TODAY. In *Эффективность применения инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве* (pp. 198-200).

43. Shaxrilloevich, I. I. (2023). DIDACTIC CONDITIONS FOR THE PREPARATION OF STUDENTS OF VOCATIONAL EDUCATION FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH. *Academia Repository*, 4(10), 142-145.

44. Шахриллоевич П (2021). Педагогические условия формирования готовности выпускников вузов к трудоустройству. *ACADEMICIA: МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ МНОГОДИСЦИПЛИНАРНЫЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ*, 11 (1), 881-884.
45. Ochilovich, S. Z. (2020, September). Inoyatov Ikrom Shaxriloyevich, Shodiyev Ne'matjon Sadirovich. Tabiiy uyulovlar va uning bugungi kundagi ahamiyati. In *Эффективность применение инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве» международная научно-практическая онлайн-конференция* (pp. 25-26).
46. Ikrom, I. (2023). KASBIY TAYYORGARLIKNING RIVOJLANISH DINAMIKASI BO'YICHA PEDAGOGIK TAJRIBA-SINOV ISHLARI NATIJALARINING TAHLILI. In *Uz-Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 626-633).
47. EUsarov, J., JEsnaev, N., OKhakimov, J., ISaidova, D., ShInoyatov, I., & SShodiev, N. (2022). THE SOCIAL SIGNIFICANCE OF CREATING A MECHANISM OF PSYCHOLOGICAL STUDY OF THE CHILDRENS SPIRIT IN CRISIS FAMILIES. *NeuroQuantology*, 20(16), 4614.
48. Musinovich, S. M. (2023, June). DRIP IRRIGATION INTENSIVE APPLE ORCHARDS AND SEASONAL WATER CONSUMPTION. In *Proceedings of Scientific Conference on Multidisciplinary Studies* (Vol. 2, No. 6, pp. 8-14).
49. Саримсаков, М. М. (2023, May). СПОСОБЫ ПОЛИВА И УРОЖАЙНОСТЬ ИНТЕНСИВНЫХ ЯБЛОНЕВЫХ САДОВ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 2, No. 14, pp. 173-175).
50. Shodiev, N. S. (2022). USE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PREPARING ENGINEERING STUDENTS FOR PROJECT-CONSTRUCTION ACTIVITY. *Экономика и социум*, (10-2 (101)), 167-169.
51. Sadirovich, S. N. (2022). The Significance of Problem Situation Assignments in Teaching the Science of Machine Details. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 3(8), 30-32.
52. Shodiyev Ziyodullo Ochilovich, & Shodiyev Nematjon Sadirovich. (2022). KINEMATIC STUDY OF FLAT BASE MECHANISMS. *E Conference Zone*, 61-69. Retrieved from <https://www.econferencezone.org/index.php/ecz/article/view/888>
53. Shodiyev Ziyodullo Ochilovich, & Shodiyev Nematjon Sadirovich. (2022). STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE DRYING PROCESS OF COTTON RAW MATERIALS. *Conferencea*, 47-50. Retrieved from <https://conferencea.org/index.php/conferences/article/view/295>
54. Shodiev, N. S. (2022). " PREPARING ENGINEERING STUDENTS FOR DESIGNCONSTRUCTION ACTIVITY THROUGH TEACHING" MACHINE DETAILS". *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 14(7).
55. Ochilovich, S. Z., Abduganievich, D. N., Nematovich, S. S., & Sadirovich, S. N. (2021). EFFECT OF FORCES ON AIR CONVEYING DEVICES AND NETWORK ON COTTON SEED QUALITY. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 771-775.
56. Nematovich, S. S., Abduganievich, D. N., & Sadirovich, S. N. (2021). TECHNOLOGY OF PRODUCTION OF CERAMIC MATERIALS AND ITS VALUE TODAY. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 768-770.
57. Ochilovich, S. Z., Abdug'aniyevich, D. N., Ne'matovich, S. S., & Sadirovich, S. N. M. (2021). Methods Of Kinematic Study of Flat Base Mechanisms. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 3, 208-214.
58. Садир Нематович Шодиев¹, Неъматжон Садирович Шодиев². (2024). ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ВЛИЯНИЯ ЗАБИВАЕМОСТИ ТРУБОК РАДИАТОРА НА ТЕПЛОВОЕ СОСТОЯНИЯ ДВИГАТЕЛЯ. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 145-151. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/32>
59. Shodiyev Ne'matjon. (2024). INTEGRATIV YONDASHUV ASOSIDA UMUMKASBIY FANLARNI O'QITISHNING ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALARI. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 945-950. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/195>
60. Shodiyev Ne'matjon. (2024). TEXNIKA OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA UMUMKASBIY FANLARNI AXBOROT TA'LIM MUHITIDA O'QITISHNING MUHIM YO'NALISHLARI. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 938-944. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/194>